

Mechanistic Insights into the Therapeutic Potential of *Colocasia esculenta* Leaves against various Pathophysiological Conditions- A Review

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Abstract The nature provide lots of gifts in form of plants which have lots of health benefits one of the traditional plant is *Colocasia esculenta* also called taro plant is very popular plant use as medicinal purpose due to its phytochemical properties and edible purpose, its good source of vitamins and minerals. The *Colocasia Esculenta* leaves have lots of phytochemical that help in treatment of various disease like flavonoid, alkaloids which help in treatment of diabetes, it also have fibres that help in treatment of lots of gastrointestinal disease etc. This study show the various pharmacological activity of *Colocasia Esculenta* leaves with its mechanism of action.

Keywords: *Colocasia Esculenta*, Phytochemical, Flavonoid, Alkaloids, GI disease, Diabetise

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

It represents the beneficial effect of *Colocasia Esculenta* leaves, includes management of diabetes due to its alpha glycosidase inhibitory effect. The huge fibres in this leaves responsible in treatment of diarrhoea and manage high cholesterol levels. The leaves also contain lots of vitamins mainly vitamin c and vitamin e which having antioxidant activity and Fe^{3+} in leaves help in treatment of Anaemia.

INTRODUCTION

Colocasia esculenta is a widely use medicinal plant of arum family. It is grow in south part of Asia and all part of India. It have heart shape and rich green leaves, size of colocasia esculenta plant 3-6 ft. tall due to big size leaves about 20-150 cm long and leaves look like elephant ear so colocasia plant leaves also called elephant ear or taro leaves.¹

The *Colocasia esculenta* leaves contains irritant not only *Colocasia esculenta* plant, all the plant of arum family also contain irritant, which cause discomfort in mouth and throat. According to Food and agriculture organization every year 6 million tons of *Colocasia Esculenta* leaves produce every year.²

It is cultivated widely across Asia, Africa, and the Pacific Islands, primarily for its starchy corms, which serve as a staple food for millions of people. The fresh leaves of taro leaves use by African society for the treatment of wounds and boils because taro leaves contain alkaloids which protect cell from inflammation and juice of stalks is used by Indonesia for several years for snakebite. Taro leaves help in reduce bleeding in arterial haemorrhage.³

However, the aerial parts of the plant, particularly the leaves, are rich in bioactive phytochemicals and possess immense ethnomedicinal value. Traditionally, *C. esculenta* leaves have been used in various indigenous systems of medicine to treat ailments such as wounds, diarrhea, inflammation, anemia, and metabolic disorders. The *Colocasia esculenta* leaves contain high fibres, vitamin a, vitamin c, vitamin e, potassium. The taro leaves contain huge amount of vitamin c which is about 52 mg in 100 g of leaves so taro leaves are very effective in treatment of deficiency of vitamin c.⁴

Recent phytochemical investigations have confirmed that the leaves contain potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory compounds capable of modulating oxidative stress pathways and immune responses. The vitamin c responsible for biosynthesis of dopamine, synthesis of neurotransmitter, nitric acid synthesis (which help in maintain of blood pressure and prevent from hypotension) and catecholamine biosynthesis.⁵

Vitamin C also have antioxidant activity because it increase activity of vitamin but the higher dose of taro leaves lead to formation of calcium oxalate crystal in kidney because vitamin c metabolise and form oxalate, these oxalate then bind to calcium in kidney and form kidney stone. The *colocasia esculenta* leaves also contain vitamin a, which is good of eyes and vitamin e which show antioxidant activity. It also contain fibres which is good for GIT.⁶

Additionally, dietary fibers present in the leaves play a significant role in glycemic regulation, lipid metabolism, and gut health. With rising interest in functional foods and plant-based therapeutics, *C. esculenta* leaves have emerged as a potential candidate for the development of novel phytopharmaceutical agents.⁷

Despite their widespread traditional use, scientific validation of the pharmacological mechanisms associated with *C. esculenta* leaves is still emerging. This review consolidates the current knowledge on the phytochemistry and therapeutic applications of *C. esculenta* leaves, with an emphasis on mechanistic insights into their roles in combating key pathophysiological conditions such as diabetes, inflammation, oxidative stress, and microbial infections.

Figure 1: Colocasia Esculenta plant.

CLASSIFICATION

Family :Araceae.

Division :Tracheophyta

Class :Liliopsida

Kingdom : Plantae.

Oder :Alismatales.

Genus : Taro.

Species : Colocasia esculenta.

Binomial name: Colocasia esculenta L

Table 1: Nutrient and Phytochemical Composition of Colocasia esculenta Leaves

Compound Type	Example Compounds	Quantity (per 100g)	Pharmacological Activity
Vitamin C	Ascorbic acid	52 mg	Antioxidant, Iron absorption
Iron (Fe ³⁺)	Ferric ion	0.22 mg	Hematinic, anti-anemic
Dietary Fiber	Soluble/insoluble	4.1 g	Hypoglycemic, Antidiarrheal
Flavonoids	Quercetin, luteolin	NA	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant
Alkaloids	Colocasinine	NA	Antidiabetic, Antimicrobial

Table 2: Summary of Mechanisms Linked to Pharmacological Activities

Health Condition	Bioactive Constituents	Mechanism of Action	References
Diabetes	Flavonoids, Alkaloids	α -glucosidase & aldose reductase inhibition	Sharma et al., 2019; Li et al.
Hyperlipidemia	Fiber, Phytosterols	Bile acid sequestration, fat absorption delay	Eneh et al., 2020
Inflammation	Quercetin, Apigenin	NF- κ B & MAPK pathway inhibition	Baro et al., 2023
Oxidative Stress	Vitamin C, Vitamin E	ROS scavenging, lipid peroxidation prevention	Mitharwal et al., 2022
Diarrhoea	Fiber	Gel formation, delayed intestinal transit	Wudali et al., 2023
Hypertension	Potassium, Nitrates	Vasodilation, NO-mediated smooth muscle relaxation	Olatunji et al., 2024
Anemia	Iron, Vitamin C, Folate	Improved absorption, hemoglobin synthesis	Ufelle et al., 2018

Various Health Benefits of Colocasia Esculenta Plant and its Mechanism

Diabetes

Diabetes mellitus is type of metabolic disorder in which decrease in insulin secretion or high insulin secretion but receptor are resistant and not show action. It is of two types, Type 1 and Type 2. In type 1 diabetes is due to autoimmune condition, the beta cell of pancreas contain HLA gene in which any foreign antigen attach, this cause T- lymphocytes come on its action and recognized the HLA because HLA act as a foreign cause cytotoxic reaction and destruction of Beta cell.⁸

In case of type 2 diabetes the insulin release from beta cell but extra glucose store in very small quantity in muscle, fat tissue and liver so that amount of glucose is more in blood, in liver extra glucose move in the presence of insulin through GLUT channel when insulin bind to receptor present on it and these extra glucose move to liver convert glucose to glycogen and store it but in type 2 diabetes receptor become resistant (not show action) cause increase in blood glucose level.⁹

Mechanism

Many research show the taro leaves have anti-diabetic activity due to presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and polyphenols because all part of plant contain Alpha-Glycosidase inhibitory activity. The alpha glycosidase enzyme present in intestine brush border and this

enzyme responsible for breakdown of carbohydrates into glucose so that glucose easily absorb into blood but taro leaves having alpha glycosidase inhibitory activity which cause slow the breakdown of carbohydrates, decrease glucose formation and absorption.¹⁰

The *Colocasia esculenta* plant rich in fibres, these fibres mix with content present in stomach and form gel like structure that means these fibres traps carbohydrates and slow down digestion which lead to decrease glucose absorption. These fibres also absorb water and increase faecal bulk, which lead increase peristaltic movement and decrease intestinal transition time cause decrease in absorption of glucose.¹¹

It also have aldose reductase enzyme inhibitory activity, the aldose reductase cause conversion Glucose to sorbitol and this sorbitol accumulate different part of body cause damage to various tissue by increase osmotic stress like damage in lens of eye cause cataracts, damage in retina cause retinopathy, damage to kidney cause nephropathy, neuropathy and nerveopathy. All this condition occurs due to decrease in sorbitol dehydrogenase activity, which decreases due high blood glucose level, which form sorbitol to fructose. The *Colocasia esculenta* prevent accumulation of sorbitol and protect organ from damage due to diabetes.¹²

Reduce Cholesterol

The cholesterol is a fat like substance made by liver also come from food that we intake and then it pack into a particle called lipoprotein. Our body need cholesterol for making hormone, vitamin d and substance that help in digestion of food called bile. The lipoprotein carry cholesterol which is LDL, VLDL and HDL. The LDL, VLDL are called bad cholesterol and HDL called good cholesterol.¹³

The LDL travel through bloodstream delivering cholesterol to the cell that need it, if body have too much LDL it build in the wall of arteries. The LDL and other substance and other substance in our arteries wall form a fatty deposits called plaque. Over a time plaque cause narrow the arteries and reduce blood flow, the most common are of plaque deposition is coronary arteries that feed our heart that cause increase the chance of heart attack.¹⁴

If plaque build-up in other arteries such as carotid arteries in neck cause reduce blood flow in brain and increase the chance of stroke. The liver also make HDL, HDL remove extra cholesterol from cell and tissue and reduce plaque, HDL return the extra cholesterol to the liver which then remove from our body so HDL called good cholesterol.¹⁵

Mechanism

As we know the cholesterol make bile and plant *Colocasia esculenta* increase the bile excretion and reduce cholesterol and it indirectly decrease the absorption of cholesterol and fatty acid because it contain fibres which mix with food content present in stomach and delay the digestion and absorption of fats.¹⁶

Reduce Inflammation

Inflammation is classically describe by four key signs swelling, redness, heat and pain, sometimes these fore signs combine cause fifth signs which is 'FunctioLaesa' which is loss of

function due to pain or swelling. The inflammation occurs due to some stimuli like pathogen, even though pathogens are the common cause of infection, which lead to inflammation. The inflammation cause by other things such as toxins and trauma example after a intense workout muscle feel sore that due to inflammation trying to repair overuse muscle fibres. The goal of inflammation is respond to stimuli and restores balance. The inflammation can be trigger by external and internal factor.¹⁷

The external factor includes allergens, irritants, toxic compound and microbial factor contain virulence factor, and pathogen associated molecule pattern. The virulence factors are the molecule that helps pathogen colonize tissue and cause infection. The Pathogen associated molecular pattern are small molecule which conserved pattern that are share across many different pathogen including bacterial wall component like peptidoglycan, LPS, lipoteichoic acid and fungal wall component like 'Mannan'. Intracellular pathogens like viruses PAMPS(Pathogen associated molecular pattern) might include viral RNA or DNA, our immune system recognized virulence factors and PAMPS as foreign substance and trigger inflammatory response against them.¹⁸

The internal factor called "Damage associated molecular patterns", these are intracellular protein that get release when cell plasma membrane get injured or when cell dies so "DAMPS" signal that there is a serious cell damage and trigger inflammation.¹⁹

Mechanism

The inflammation occur through MAPK pathway and MAPK cause phosphorylation of ERK, JNK and p38 and degradation of I κ B α which cause dissociation of NF- κ B form I κ B α and NF- κ B move to nucleus show transcription and translation lead to formation of cytokines cause inflammation but taro leaves contain lots of flavonoids which reduce MAPK activity and decrease phosphorylation of ERK, JNK and P38 protein and NF- κ B not dissociate(inactive form) lead to decrease in cytokines production.²⁰

Use in diarrhoea

The diarrhoea is a condition in which patient suffered from watery stool or bloody stool, which cause huge loss of electrolyte from body. The diarrhoea is of two types first is bloody diarrhoea and watery diarrhoea. The bloody diarrhoea occur due to some bacteria like E.coli, Shigella, the bacteria move into the lumen of intestine and release enterotoxins, which bind to the mucosal cell of intestine and inhibit the protein synthesis cause mucosal cell death. Due to increase in permeability in mucosal cell, the bacteria with its enterotoxins move toward the blood vessel and cause damage in endothelial cell, which lead to blood pass from mucosal cell to lumen and pass with stool.²¹

The watery diarrhoea is condition in which loss of electrolytes which occur due to increase in CAMP level in villous cell which cause release of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in lumen of intestine and some time there is increase in prostaglandin in mucosal cell, these prostaglandin show secretion activity and promote the release of HCO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ from crypt cell to lumen also promote the release of more sodium and chloride. The other reason is bacteria which is V.cholerae enter into lumen of intestine and mucosal cell insert K⁺ channel and lead to release of K⁺ in lumen. All this condition there is increase in positive charge to lumen of intestine and water is

release from blood stream to lumen to neutralize the charge, which cause stool become watery and loss of electrolyte.²²

Mechanism

In case of diarrhoea the stool become watery the taro plant contain lots of fibres which absorb the stomach content, swell and increase bulk of stool which cause slow down the movement of stool.²³

Antioxidant activity

Oxidative stress is a condition when there is an imbalance between free radical production antioxidant activity, i.e., a decrease in antioxidative activity of the body and an increase in free radicals. As we know, normally oxygen is converted into superoxide anion radical, which is then converted into hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radical and finally converted to water. That way, the body protects itself from oxidative stress.²⁴

These oxygen radicals produce oxidative stress in two ways: Firstly, these superoxide radicals produce damage by themselves or by activating other types of products, which also act as free radicals. The free radicals are the molecular fragments that contain one or more unpaired electrons. They are highly reactive (causing the generation of new radicals) and have a short life span, which leads to damage to other tissue. The ROS can steal electrons from enzymes, which causes alterations in the function or structure of the enzyme/protein and also damages DNA by stealing electrons from DNA. The ROS also take electrons from the membrane that lead to charge imbalance in the membrane and create a free radical cascade in the membrane. This is called lipid peroxidation that creates damage in the membrane²⁵.

Another way of free radical generation is activation of nitric oxide synthase which activate when there is exposure of stressful condition, this nitric oxide synthase convert Arginine into Nitric oxide radical that also cause damage.²⁶

Mechanism

The whole plant of colocasia esculenta show antioxidant activity mainly leaves because it contains vitamin E and Vitamin C. The reduced vitamin e react with lipid peroxy radical form Lipid hydro-peroxy radical and vitamin e get oxidize. This way vitamin e reduce lipid peroxidation damage and role of vitamin c is to convert oxidize vitamin e into reduced vitamin e which increase action of vitamin e.²⁷

Figure 2: This figure show the how vitamin c and vitamin e show anti - oxidative effect

The Vitamin C also show antioxidant activity by following ways-

A) When vitamin c (ascorbate) react with supeoxide radical it form hydrogen peroxide and monodehydroascorbate.

B) When vitamin c (ascorbate) react with hydroxyl radical it form water and monodehydroascorbate.

Hypertension

The hypertension means high blood pressure, the blood pressure is the force of circulating blood exert on the wall of vessels. It includes systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure because of pumping action of heart, the pressure within the arteries cycle between a higher pressure and lower pressure. The higher pressure occurs during the contraction of heart left ventricle. The higher pressure is known as the systolic blood pressure, the lower pressure occur during the relaxation of heart left ventricle²⁸.

This lower pressure refers to diastolic blood pressure. The normal blood pressure is below 140/90 and above this range called hypertension. The blood pressure due to primary causes or secondary causes, the primary causes includes stress conditions and genetics and secondary causes include disease like heart disease or kidney disease²⁹.

Mechanism

The plant colocasia esculenta contain potassium which help in main blood pressure because when potassium enter into cell cause closure of sodium channel lead to membrane repolarization phase that relax heart and reduce blood pressure³⁰.

The taro leaves also involve in formation nitric acid, which is use in treatment of angina pectoris because they cause vasodilation of vessels and decrease load of heart, these nitric acid release nitrate ion in lumen of the vein with the help of certain enzyme the nitrate ion converted to nitric oxide and the nitric oxide is a hydrophobic gas having short half-life which move to smooth muscle cell of venous wall. Inside the smooth muscle cell nitric oxide activate the guanylyl cyclase which cause converting of GTP to CGMP, the cyclic CGMP activate the CGMP dependent protein kinase which lead to dephosphorylating of MLCK chain and this nitric oxide also decrease cytosolic calcium by prevent release from sarcoplasmic reticulum and increase calcium efflux both lead to smooth muscle relaxation.

In Anaemia

The anaemia is define as reduction in red blood cell mass but in practical the measurement of red blood cell mass is difficult so anaemia diagnosed based on reduction in haemoglobin concentration. The concentration of haemoglobin varies according to gender, the male having 13g/dl, female having 11.5g/dl and new-born having 15g/dl below these concentration the person supposed to anaemic³¹.

The symptoms include tiredness, easy fatigability, generalised muscular weakness, lethargy, and headache and in older patients, there may be symptoms of cardiac failure, angina pectoris, confusion and visual disturbance. This anaemia is of morphologically three types a) Microcytic, hypochromic b) Normocytic, normochromic c) Macrocytic, normochromic³².

The normal size of RBC is 7 micro-meter of diameter and there is no nucleus in the RBC. The haemoglobin is present in periphery of RBC, the peripheral two third of RBC covered with haemoglobin and central one third is white in colour. The RBC is analyse under the microscope by making the slide, as we know blood also contain lymphocytes and size of RBC is same as lymphocytes. If the RBC size not same as lymphocytes its indicate anaemia. In case of microcytic RBC is smaller than the lymphocytes, in macrocytic RBC size is larger than lymphocytes but in case of normocytic RBC size is normal³³.

Mechanism

The per leaves of taro leaves contain approx. 0.22 milligram of iron and 12.6 microgram of folic acid present in taro leaves. The taro leaves contain Fe³⁺ form of iron, when Fe³⁺ move to the stomach with the help of stomach acid Fe³⁺ converted to Fe²⁺. The Fe²⁺ move to intestine and absorbed in the intestinal cell with the help of DMT (Divalent metal transporter) then Fe²⁺ move to blood with the help of Ferroportin. When fe²⁺ move to blood it again converted into fe³⁺ and bind to its transporter called Transferrin, this transporter carrying iron into bone marrow and pluripotent hematopoietic stem cell utilise iron to form heme in each phase of RBC and help in formation of haemoglobin³⁴.

The taro leaves also contain ascorbic acid, which increase the iron absorption because it help in conversion of Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺ and it also have small amount of folic acid which indirectly help in treatment of Megaloblastic anaemia. That is why taro leaves help in treatment of anaemia.³⁵

CONCLUSION

The Colocasia esculenta is a good source of vitamins and minerals, daily consumption of Colocasia esculent leaves provide many health benefit due to phytochemical present on it which is identify by using various phytochemical test, due to alkaloid, polyphenols and tannins second it have aldose reduce activity that why it show anti- diabetes properties and Colocasia esculenta have flavonoids like luteolin, apigenin etc which help in protection from inflammation by reduce the cytokines release. The Colocasia esculenta leaves is good source of Vitamin C about 100 g colocasia esculenta leaves contain 52 mg of Vitamin c which help in treatment of scurvy and show antioxidant activity. Colocasia esculenta leaves is rich source of fibres which help in management of blood cholesterol level, diarrhoea and diabetes, it also have iron which is use in treatment of anaemia.

AUTHORS'S CONTRIBUTION

Shantanu Shukla : Data curation, methodology and both the original draft and review of the writing.

Monika: Conceptualization, formal analysis and editing of the writing.

Neeraj Kumar: Formal analysis and Drafting.

Divya Juyal: Supervision and review.

All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS -

GIT - Gastrointestinal Tract

Fe³⁺ - Ferric ion

HLA - Human Leukocyte Antigen

GLUT - Glucose Transporter

LDL - Low-Density Lipoprotein

HDL - High-Density Lipoprotein

LPS - Lipopolysaccharide

PAMPS - Pathogen-Associated Molecular Patterns

DAMPS -Damage-Associated Molecular Patterns

MAPK - Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase

ERK -Extracellular signal-Regulated Kinase

JNK -c-Jun N-terminal Kinase

NF- κ B -Nuclear Factor Kappa B

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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